
Pest management and control DISEASES

Collateral hosts of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn causing sheath blight of rice

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Sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* has assumed endemic proportions in most rice growing areas in Kerala. We recorded *R. solani* incidence on plants grown in rice fallows and on common lowland weeds at several sites.

Plant parts showing *R. solani* symptoms were cut into small pieces, surface sterilized in 0.1% mercuric chloride, washed in 3 changes of sterile water, and transferred to sterile petri dishes containing potato dextrose agar (PDA). The *R. solani* isolates obtained were purified

using the hyphal tip method and maintained on PDA slants. Pathogenicity of the isolates was established by artificial inoculation on their respective host plants. The following plants were found to be collateral hosts of *R. solani*: *Sesamum indicum* L., *Arachis hypogaea* L., *Sesbania aculeata* Pers., wild colocasia, *Cyperus iria* L., *Fimbristylis miliacea* Vahl, *Apluda aristata* L., and *Monochoria vaginalis* Burm. F. Presl.

R. solani produced severe collar rot symptoms on *Sesamum* and caused severely infected plants to wilt and die. The fungus caused severe leaf and stem blight on groundnut *A. hypogaea*. Badly infected leaves were shed prematurely. On *S. aculeata*, the fungus produced severe collar rot symptoms at all plant growth stages.

Infected wild colocasia plants growing

in and around rice fields developed typical ShB symptoms on the petiole. The fungus caused leaf blight on *C. iria* and *F. miliaceae*. Dark-colored lesions were observed on the leaf sheath and leaves of *A. aristata*. The fungus caused typical ShB symptoms on the petioles of *M. vaginalis*. Cross-inoculation studies on rice plants showed that all the eight *R. solani* isolates listed, except that from *S. indicum*, produced typical ShB symptoms.

A. aristata and *M. vaginalis* are new weed hosts of *R. solani* in India. This is the first record of this fungus causing collar rot symptoms on *S. aculeata*. On groundnut in India, *R. solani* has not yet been recorded to cause leaf and stem blight under natural conditions.

Eliminating collateral weed hosts can help reduce the inoculum potential of the ShB pathogen. □

Morphology and serological relationship of penyakit merah virus in Malaysia and rice tungro virus in the Philippines

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Penyakit merah (red disease) (PMV) of rice plants in Malaysia and rice tungro (RTV) in the Philippines have several common properties, including symptoms, varietal reactions and transmission by the vector green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*.

When we examined leaf dip preparations of PMV using 2% phosphotungstic acid on carbon-coated grids under an electron microscope, two morphologically distinct viral particles were detected. One was isometric and about 31-37 nm in diameter. The other was bacilliform and about 35 nm in diameter, with length varying from 148 to 175 nm. There usual-

ly were more isometric particles. The particles are similar to those associated with RTV in the Philippines, penyakit hebang in Indonesia, and yellow-orange leaf in Thailand.

The serological relationship between PMV and RTV was examined using latex

flocculation test. Positive reactions were detected when leaf extracts of PMV-infected rice plants were tested with latex sensitized with rice tungro bacilliform virus and/or rice tungro spherical virus, indicating that PMV and RTV are also caused by the two viruses. □

Sheath blight occurrence in rice nurseries

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Sheath blight (ShB) has damaged rice since 1979 in kharif and rabi seasons in West and East Godavari Districts. It reached epidemic levels in 1981 kharif and 1982 rabi, when it affected all varieties grown and significantly reduced yield. In early ShB infections, only adult plants at panicle initiation stage were affected. Since 1981 kharif wet nurseries have been affected at the research farm and in some farmers fields.

In 1981 and 1982 MTU8002 (Gouthami), MTU8089 (Vashista), MTU7029

(Swarna), MTU4569 (Sowbhagya), MTU-4407 (Vijaya Mahsuri), IR42, and IR36 and prerelease cultures MTU5 182, MTU-7633, IET6314, and IET7574 were severely affected in the nursery. In 1982-83 rabi no nursery infection was observed.

Most seedlings in the nursery had infected lower leaves but some had sheath and leaf infection. Seedling infection followed a normal pattern. Severe infection caused stunting. *Leersia hexandra* growing as a weed in the infected nursery also had typical ShB symptoms.

We studied the possible carry-over of nursery infection to adult plants by transplanting 30- to 35-day-old infected seedlings of 13 cultures. We recorded damage at regular intervals, starting 5 days after transplanting (DT). Healthy MTU7029